

Eurodoc Response on the Future of FP10 and ERC

The European Commission's plan to restructure the organisation of R&I funding as [reported in ScienceBusiness](#) is alarming. The claim that this serves to put science, development, and innovation at the centre seems but a fig leaf. What actually puts science, development, and innovation at the centre of the EU's innovation strategy is [making the necessary financial investments](#) and not a top-down restructuring. The three pillar structure is considered a success: The European Research Council (ERC) has been effective in stimulating and ensuring research excellence, with both the ERC's independence and the ringfenced budget protecting the freedom to scientific research. Defence research has not just a different logic than fundamental and blue-sky research, it is also tied to shifting political priorities, making it crucial to ensure the separation of budgets. Instead of nice catchphrases, realising the goal set two decades ago, namely that each member state devotes 3% of their GDP to R&I and increasing the funding by the EU will ensure that Europe sees the stimulation, impact, and innovation it expects from research.

The scope of funding for FP10

Horizon Europe plays a central role in stimulating economic growth and innovation: Each euro invested generates a return of up to €11 in GDP over 25 years.¹ The programmes should thus be kept as stable as possible and as flexible as necessary in order to fully achieve the goals of the strategic plan. The primary goal has to be to close Europe's gap vis-a-vis other regions in the world in terms of R&I investments: **Throwing the current structures over board might give the appearance of political activity for R&I, in reality it simply veils what is generally known to be the actual crux, namely that the R&I budget is not being increased in the dimensions necessary.** Experienced stakeholder organisations across the research and innovation sector as well as MEPs intimately familiar with R&I such as Christian Ehler and Maria da Graça Carvalho have called for a robust FP10 budget of €200 billion for good reasons. For years, the Member States have been called upon to live up to the target they set over two decades ago, namely to devote 3% of their GDP to R&I. Reviewing the [responses to FP10](#), it becomes overwhelmingly clear that the structure with the three pillars is considered fundamentally a success and – while needing further adjustments and calibrations – should be maintained.

The problem is not the structure, nor the lack of competitiveness, nor the lack of research excellence – it is the persistent underfunding of R&I. According to recent figures on the Horizon Europe implementation (2021-2023), only 33% of the high-quality proposals² can be funded. The ex-post evaluation of Horizon 2020 equally showed that an additional €159 billion would have been necessary to finance all the high-quality proposals that should have received funding. **In other words, as Maria Leptine stated in a recent interview, more than half of the projects that should be funded and that could provide exactly the impact for European**

¹ Horizon Europe strategic plan 2025-2027 analysis, p.9. The Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) plans €47.4 billion in R&I. At this stage, out of the 608 R&I-related targets set, 98 have been completed and 36 have already been assessed as met. See COM/2023/277 final.

² Extrapolated to the entire Horizon Europe period, a budget of even €290 billion (instead of the available budget of €95.5 billion) would be needed to fund them all.

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society and economy the Commission President is calling for cannot be realised because of budget constraints.

Noticeably, the European Research Council has been operating with the same funding levels since 2007. **ERC grants have not been corrected for inflation since, meaning in practice a decrease in funding per project** – with particular consequences for large-scale research projects. Similarly, the **Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) can only fund a fraction of the high-quality proposals** in the submissions they receive. For MSCA, the problem thus is equally not quality and competitiveness, but underfunding – particularly in light of inflation. In light of this, [LERU and others](#) thus recommends that a mechanism is put in place to update unit costs more frequently, and Flanders requests that the country coefficient is updated to ensure the grants cover the rising salary levels of researchers and to safeguard the attractiveness of the MSCA.

The importance of an independent ERC and MSCA

The ERC together with the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) are the **only programmes available for conducting bottom-up, curiosity-driven, and ground-breaking research at the frontier of knowledge**. Both have demonstrated their exceptional ability to identify excellence in Europe and thereby furthering the societal and economic impact of research.

With the MSCA being targeted towards early career researchers, it is **the backbone of the future of research and development in Europe**. It also plays a significant role in promoting 'brain circulation' across Europe. Thus it is a **key instrument for strengthening the fifth freedom** as it facilitates **internationalisation, interdisciplinarity, and intersectoral mobility**. MSCAA thus uniquely connects these three mobilities at the heart of European research with the advancement of research careers.

The Scientific Council's **independence has been critical to the ERC's success**. This independence entails the ability to determine how the ERC's calls are run and how its grants can be managed according to the needs of frontier research and responsive to a changing world. A single governance and a single rulebook covering eligibility rules and third-party participation on this scale risks failing to provide streamlining and efficiency, while also failing to be able to provide evaluations that respond to the specific requirements of excellence, the scopes of the different disciplines and projects, and a dynamic research sector – as the ERC has been able to do, whereby it has also ensured the excellence of the larger research community. The ERC being steered by an independent Scientific Council with a dedicated agency for implementation means **guaranteeing the quality of the ERC's operations and above all its peer review processes**. This in turn not only ensures the ERC's **credibility in the scientific community**, but remains equally fundamental to **build societal trust in research** in the long term. The ERC's independence and autonomy must be protected under FP10 to safeguard its position as Europe's top frontier research funder. For the future of research excellence in Europe, the ERC should be bolstered to remain the most attractive and highly prestigious grant, so it can continue its excellent work for making innovative research possible in the first place, namely attracting the very best talents – also from outside the EU.

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Protecting freedom to scientific research in EU democracies: Ringfenced budgets and the retention of the three-pillar structure

Rather than squeezing everything into a super-budget, it is crucial to retain the three pillar structure and to ringfence and protect the budget within FP10 – not least to **prevent the diversion of the research budget to emerging or shifting political priorities**. Considering that already this year, €1.5 billion of the research and innovation framework programme budget had been diverted to defence research by EU heads of state this is not an unlikely possibility. Putting FP10, space, defence research, and innovation funds in one super-budget would mean that in the future funding can much more easily and with significantly less visibility be shifted for political and industry interests. **This will not put science and innovation at the centre – even if this is what many want to hear. The catchphrase is nothing more than a shrew governmental figment of a carrot, so the stick is less visible: the threat to funding allocated to fundamental and blue-sky research.**

Thinking that defence research can be treated under the same rulebook and governance as FP10 belies any learnings from our own European history. It is not because the research community and policy makers enjoy cumbersome rules. Rather, it is to ensure that research and higher education remains in the service of European democracies and civil society that attentive and circumspect regulations have been put in place for defence and dual use research.

No amount of restructuring will cover up inadequate funding

Long-term continuity and the increase of the budget according to the targets will enable the blue-sky research that allows orientation towards the future – not a mega-structure. Neither public trust, nor trust from the research community and the industry can be built through overhauling functioning structures once again. **The single-minded return to a simplistic call for increased competitiveness and neoliberal so-called governmental streamlining** does not put science, innovation, and technology at the centre. What would do so, however, is the EU and its member states actually following through with delivering on their own targets set 20 years ago: **[Making the necessary financial investments](#) in research, innovation, and education.**

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